

EFFECT OF ROLLING TEMPERATURE ON SHEAR STRENGTH OF HOT ROLL BONDED TI/STEEL CLAD PLATES WITH VANADIUM AND IF STEEL INTERLAYER

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ABSTRACT

Ti/steel clad plates with V and IF steel interlayer successfully fabricated by hot roll bonding process. Clad plates with different rolling temperature were investigated by using SEM and XRD. Results show that V-Ti and V-Fe solid solutions formed at interfaces rather than intermetallic compounds (IMCs), rolling temperature has a significant influence on shear strength of clad plates. When rolling temperature is 850 °C, shear strength value of clad plates is the highest because V/Ti and V/steel interface achieved well bonded, cracks spread in Ti layer during shear test. When rolling temperature is 900 °C, cracks also spread in Ti layer, shear strength value of clad plates is lower because higher rolling temperature augments grains of Ti. As rolling temperature increased to 950 °C, hardness value of V interlayer is extremely low because of recrystallization process happened in this layer, at the same time, V-Fe solid solution contains abundant of Fe is another crack-susceptible region. Specimens bonded at 950 °C reported the lowest shear strength value.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ti/steel clad plates had been widely used in chemical and nuclear industrials because of outstanding mechanical properties and corrosion resistance [1-4]. For example, chimneys in coal-fired power plants are made of Ti/steel clad plates to prevent chimneys from corrosion.

Among the methods to fabricate clad plates, solid-state bonding techniques such as diffusion bonding, explosion bonding, roll bonding are most used methods. During diffusion bonding process, irregular shaped micro-voids were observed at interface due to the different diffusion coefficient of Fe and Ti [5], which were called "Kirkendal voids". Generally, voids at interface reduce shear strength of clad plates. The ideal way to bond different materials is roll bonding. On one hand, principles of this process are

simpler compared with other bonding methods. On the other hand, roll bonding process can improve microstructures of plates, since voids at interfaces and other flaws can be eliminated. Moreover, roll bonding technology is a bonding technology that is able to manufacture large scale products. It meets the requirements of industrial production. Plenty of parameters are able to affect the shear strength of clad plates fabricated by roll bonding. One of the most important parameters is rolling temperature, which determines the kinds and the thickness of intermetallic compounds (IMCs) at interface. Hot roll bonded Ti/stainless steel clad plates with Nb interlayer was investigated. Nb/Fe interface was free from IMCs until rolling temperature up to 900 °C. The formation of FeNb compound at elevated rolling temperature causes the decrease of shear strength [6]. In general, the generation kinetics of IMCs is relative to temperature, IMCs at interface would impair shear strength of clad plates because they are vulnerable to deformation. Cracks tend to spread along IMCs during deformation.

Interface in Ti/steel clad plate is a promising research field, IMCs are generated at Ti/steel interface due to the limited solubility of Ti in Fe at solid state, and vice versa. Literatures reported that the generation of IMCs at interface deteriorated the shear strength of clad plates [7]. For example, researchers successfully bonded Ti-6Al-4V to AISI 316L stainless steel and found that cracks tend to spread along IMCs such as FeTi and Fe₂Ti [8]. This is the reason why clad plates had a lower shear strength than that of the base material. In order to prevent interface from generating unfavorable IMCs, interlayers were placed between Ti and steel. Ti/steel clad plates with silver interlayer were studied by former researchers [9]. Interface shear strength of this clad plate was dissatisfactory because silver interlayer was vulnerable at elevated temperature. Further, Nb/Cu/Ni multi-interlayer Ti/steel clad plates were manufactured by diffusion bonding [10]. Ti-Fe compounds were vanished at interface when rolling temperature was 850 °C, thus leading a satisfactory shear strength. However, because of complicated structure, this kind of clad plate is still beyond application. Candidates for interlayer material which do not form IMCs with Ti are: V, Zr, Mo, Ta and so on. The most widely used material is V. On one hand, V forms continuous solid solution with Ti, a well bonded V/Ti interface is predictable. On the other hand, expansion coefficients of Ti and V are similar (Ti: 8.6, V: 8.3), which means less residual stress at the interface.

In present work, hot roll bonded Ti/steel clad plates were fabricated by hot roll bonding process at different rolling temperature. V was selected as interlayer material. Another interlayer material is interstitial-free steel (IF steel) which capable of fantastic deformability. What is more, the content of C in the IF steel is little. Compounds like VC and TiC were assumed to not generated.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Commercial pure Ti and Q235 steel were chosen to manufacture the clad plates. In addition, pure V and IF steel were selected as interlayer materials. The surfaces of each plate were brushed by steel brushes then degreased by pure alcohol. Size of plates is shown in Table 1. As shown in Figure 1, for the sake of balancing the deformation of plates during roll bonding process, Ti plate was covered by top and bottom steel plates. Segregating material was painted between top steel plate and Ti plate in order to separate top steel plate from Ti/steel clad plate. V foil was placed adjacent to Ti plate and IF steel foil was placed between V foil and bottom steel plate. After that, steel plates were welded together and pumped to vacuum condition. The semi-finished blanks were heat up to 850 °C, 900 °C and 950 °C,

respectively, and hold for 360 minutes. After 12 rolling passes, the plates were rolled together. The total rolling reduction in thickness was 94%.

For microstructure examination, specimens were grinded by using abrasive papers then polished by using diamond polishing pastes. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used to observe the interfaces. Vicer's hardness test was used to test the hardness of specimens. Shear tests were performed on a universal testing machine by using a velocity of 0.1 mm/min. The specimen size for shear tests is schematically illustrated in Figure 1 (b). After shear tests, fracture surfaces were tested by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and SEM equipped with energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS).

Plates	Outline size(mm)	Thickness(mm)
Top steel plate	140×190	18
Ti plate	100×150	20
V foil	100×150	0.02
IF steel foil	100×150	0.02
Bottom steel plate	140×190/100×150	38/18

Table 1: Size of plates.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic diagram of assembly process; (b) schematic diagram of shear test specimen.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows microstructures of Ti/steel clad plates roll bonded at different rolling temperature. As shown in Figure 2 (a) and (b), grains locate near the interface are smaller than the grains far away from the interface. In Ti layer, shear band is observed when rolling temperature is 900 °C. Generation of shear bands is the result of compatible deformation. Deformation of Ti grain near interface is restricted by friction between Ti and Fe. In order to coordinate deformation of dissimilar metals, shear deformation is activated. The shear stress leads to activation of slip systems other than those activated under plane strain compression. The result is morphologically different microstructures [11-12]. With increasing strain, dislocation cells were developed into ultrafine sub-grains. In Figure 2 (c), as rolling temperature is 950 °C, recrystallization take place in the specimen. Sub-grains near the interface are replaced by recrystallized grains. Figure 3 is backscatter images of Ti/steel clad plates with different rolling temperature. At V/Ti interface, V-Ti solid solution layer is formed when rolling temperature is 850 °C, this layer is getting thicker with the increase of rolling temperature.

Figure 2: Microstructures of Ti/steel clad plates bonded at different rolling temperature: (a) 850 °C; (b) 900 °C; (c) 950 °C.

Figure 3: Backscatter images of Ti/steel clad plates bonded at different rolling temperature: (a) 850 °C; (b) 900 °C; (c) 950 °C.

Thickness of diffusion region has a significant influence on shear strength of clad plates. A narrow diffusion region means unsatisfactory bonding. In contrast, diffusion region is vulnerable to crack if this area is too wide [13]. EDS element line scan profiles of interfaces are shown in Figure 4. Diffusion region in which the composition changes gradually was formed at interfaces. Terrace was not observed in the line, which means IMCs were not formed at diffusion region. The slope of V element distribution line tends to gentle with the increase of rolling temperature. Diffusion distance of V atoms at V/Ti and V/Fe interfaces were measured and displayed in Figure 5. The diffusion distance increase straightly with the increase of rolling temperature. According to diffusion kinetics, mutual diffusion coefficients of atoms were improved with increase of temperature, thus enhancing mutual diffusion probability of

atoms [14]. In this experiment, as samples were bonded with same rolling parameters expect for rolling temperature, the difference of diffusion distance is mainly determined by rolling temperature. Another notable phenomenon is that diffusion distance of V atoms in Ti is longer than that in Fe, and the disparity is bigger at elevated rolling temperature. It can be attribute to well solid solubility of V in Ti. Another reason is that, as the size of V atom and Ti atom is similar, V atoms only exist in Ti matrix when there are vacancies. Former researchers already found that plastic deformation induced vacancies could give rise to a significant increase of alloy elements diffusion across interface [15]. As sub-grains formed in Ti layer, so density of vacancy at this region is bigger. For this point, the diffusion of V atoms in Ti matrix is improved.

Figure 4: Line spectrum spectrogram of interfaces in Ti/steel clad plates bonded at different rolling temperature: (a) 850 °C; (b) 900 °C; (c) 950 °C.

Figure 5: Diffusion distance of V atoms at V/Ti and V/Fe interfaces bonded at different rolling temperatures.

The distribution of Vickers micro-hardness value across interfaces is shown in Figure 6. When rolling temperature is 850 °C, hardness value started with 170 HV in Ti layer and increase drastically in V layer. The value can reach about 260 HV. More remarkable, hardness value of specimen which was bonded at 950 °C is lowest. V interlayer in this specimen is softer than Ti and steel matrix, which is caused by

recrystallization in this layer. Hardness value of V/Ti and V/steel interfaces is greater than Ti and steel matrix because of solution strengthening. V and Ti can form continuous solid solution, V-Fe system also shows large regions of continuous solid solution.

Figure 6: Hardness value across interfaces of Ti/steel clad plates bonded at different rolling temperatures.

Shear strength is a crucial parameter to evaluate the mechanical properties of clad plates. Shear strength was tested by shear test at ambient temperature. Results of shear tests are displayed in Table 2. There exists an inverse relationship between shear strength and rolling temperature. Specimen bonded at 850 °C has the highest shear strength, which is around 230 MPa.

In Figure 7 (a) and (b), the fracture surfaces of specimen bonded at 850 °C were dominated by Ti. Fe element was not detected at fracture surfaces. Plenty of cleavage planes can be found on the fracture surfaces, indicating that brittle fracture is the dominant fracture mode in this specimen. Ti layer and steel layer obtained from specimen bonded at 850 °C were dominated by Ti, plenty of cleavage planes at the surfaces are attributed to little deformation of Ti, indicates that brittle fracture is the dominant fracture mode in the specimen. Fe element was not detected at fracture surfaces. The distribution of elements at fractures surfaces illustrates that V/Ti and V/steel interfaces achieved well bonded when rolling temperature is 850 °C. Additionally, the shear strength of bonding interfaces and steel layer are both bigger than that of Ti. Therefore, during shear deformation Ti layer is fractured rather than bonding interfaces or steel layer. Similar phenomenon was observed in Figure 7 (c) and (d). However, in Figure 7 (c), Ti layer shows characteristic of plastic deformation. This may be related to the fact that the Ti grains near bonding interface is bigger in this rolling temperature. Bigger grains lead to the reduction of shear strength of Ti, which further decrease the shear strength of the clad plate. Fractures of specimen bonded at 950 °C display different morphology and chemical compositions. Three areas can be distinguished according to the EDS results, namely Ti, V and V-Fe solid solution (V: 29 at. %, Fe: 71 at. %). Literature reported that Fe and V can form solid solutions and these solid solutions are crack-susceptible if the quantity of Fe is superior to 30 at. % [16]. In the meantime, Fe-V system contains metastable σ -phase, which is existed in temperature range of 650–1219 °C. Research reported that the generation of σ -phase can be avoid by rapid cooling process. In this experiment, specimens were cooled

in room temperature after roll bonding process. The σ -phase eliminated at this cooling rate, which is confirmed by the results of XRD in Figure 8 (e) and (f). In addition, hardness value at V/Fe interface is lower than the hardness value of FeV phase (1073 HV) [17]. It can conclude that V/Fe interface is free from FeV phase when rolling temperature is 950 °C. In the meanwhile, hardness value of V interlayer is extremely low. We believed that the V layer is crack-susceptible region during shear tests.

Rolling temperature (°C)	Shear strength (MPa)	Standard deviation (MPa)
850	230.7	12.9
900	190.9	15.3
950	169.9	30.3

Table 2: Shear strength value of specimens bonded at different rolling temperatures.

Figure 7: Fracture surfaces of specimens after shear test: (a) 850 °C Ti layer; (b) 850 °C steel layer; (c) 900 °C Ti layer; (d) 900 °C steel layer; (e) 950 °C Ti layer; (f) 950 °C steel layer.

Figure 8: XRD spectra of fracture surfaces: (a) 850 °C Ti layer; (b) 850 °C steel layer; (c) 900 °C Ti layer; (d) 900 °C steel layer; (e) 950 °C Ti layer; (f) 950 °C steel layer.

4. CONCLUSION

Ti/steel clad plates with V and IF steel interlayer successfully manufactured by roll bonding process. Only V-Ti and V-Fe solid solutions were formed at interfaces. Rolling temperature has a significant influence on shear strength of clad plates. The shear strength decrease with the increase of rolling temperature.

When rolling temperature is 850 °C, V/Ti and V/steel interfaces achieved well bonded, and cracks spread in Ti layer. When rolling temperature is 900 °C, cracks also spread in Ti layer, as Ti grains near the bonding interface is bigger, which leading to a lower shear strength. As rolling temperature increased to 950 °C, the specimen has the lowest shear strength. The reason is that completed recrystallization happened in V interlayer, which causing extremely low hardness value in V interlayer. In this case, it failed to withstand certain load. At the same time, V-Fe solid solution containing abundant of Fe is another crack-susceptible region.

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